

PRINCIPLES OF ACCOUNTING – QUICK CASES

UNIT 2: ETHICAL CASE 2. VALUE CREATION, SYSTEMS THINKING AND INTEGRATION

Authors: Nadia Gulko, University of Lincoln, Karen McBride, University of Portsmouth, Nick McGuigan, Monash University.

CASE OUTLINE

Figure 1: United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (UN SDGs)

Designing for Renewable Energy: Implementing Offshore Wind Park Economic, Social and Governance informed Decision-making

1. Gather into groups of five with each group member choosing one of the following UN SDGs (as shown in Figure 1):
 - a) Goal No. 7: Affordable and Clean Energy,
 - b) Goal No. 8: Decent work and economic growth,
 - c) Goal No. 9: Industry, innovation and infrastructure,
 - d) Goal No. 12: Responsible Production and Consumption,

e) Goal No. 14: Life below Water.

2. Each group member needs to undertake independent research on their chosen UN SDG. A good place to start is [here](#).
3. **Role:** Group members are on the board of directors of a conventional power generator and must reach consensus on the following case. During the discussion, every board member is required to act as an ambassador of their chosen SDG.
4. **Case scenario:** Your company would like to 'green' its operations. An opportunity has arisen to buy an insolvent company whose only major asset is a license for a huge offshore wind park. The site is situated off the coast of an economically depressed region which would financially benefit from the construction and ongoing operation of the offshore wind farm. Environmentalists warn about the risk to the marine biodiversity, and the impact on the already struggling local fishermen who would lose another fishing area.
5. **Task:** You have 25 mins to come up with a solution weighing up the five goals.

You have 5 mins to present to class your case, the goals and your solution, pointing out the tensions and synergies between the five goals. Can you articulate the different types of values you are advocating for? Could you integrate the UN SDGs? What makes this so complex?